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THE RUSSIAN HOTEL INDUSTRY: CONDITION AND DEVELOPMENT

ИНДУСТРИЯ ГОСТЕПРИИМСТВА В РОССИИ:
СОСТОЯНИЕ И РАЗВИТИЕ

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Аннотация. Целью статьи является изучение состояния и развития российской гостиничной индустрии. В ходе исследования были проанализированы факторы внутренней и внешней среды, которые оказывают существенное влияние на развитие гостиничного бизнеса в России. Среди основных проблем развития гостиничного бизнеса в России выделяют проблемы, связанные с факторами, как макроэкономического характера, так и микроэкономического характера, а также политические нестабильности. Конкурентные преимущества российской гостиничной индустрии в основном заключаются в изменении системы взаимодействия между работодателями и системой высшего образования. Помимо этого, наблюдаются изменения в системе подготовки кадров. Настоящий анализ также показывает дальнейшее развитие российской гостиничной индустрии.

Abstract. The aim of the article is to study the condition and development of the Russian hotel industry. The factors of internal and external environment that exert the great influence onto the development of the hotel business in Russia were analyzed. The main problems of the development of the hotel business in Russia related to the factors of both macro–economic and micro–economic characters and some political instabilities. The competitive advantages of the Russian hotel industry include mainly changes in the system of interaction between employers and higher education system and changes in the system of personnel training. Present analysis also shows the further development of the Russian hotel industry.

Keywords: Hotels, Tourism, Hotel management, Competencies, Prospects for further development.

Ключевые слова: отели, туризм, гостиничный менеджмент, компетентность, перспективы дальнейшего развития.

As the hotel industry and tourism are connected and quite dynamic activities (according to the Future Traveler Tribes, by 2030, there will be an extra billion people in the world, of which 20% will be travelling), it is necessary to understand which factors in the long view will have the greatest impact on it and how to increase the role of the service sector in Russia. Moreover, we should know about the main problems of the development of the hotel business in the country.

*Material and methods**The factors of external and internal environment*

The hotel industry does not function in a vacuum. It has to react to what happens outside the business. These factors are known as the factors of external and internal environment. The factors of internal environment consist of the factors onto which the hotel management can influence directly (for example standards of service, problems with staff, renovation of the hotel and etc.). The factors of external environment consist of factors of external environment of indirect (characteristics of society onto which the hotel management cannot influence directly but, however, they may have a decisive influence onto any further prospects) and direct (for example the situation with the clients, who would like some discounts, or loyal cards) effect. (Zaitseva 2013, 328.) So, it means that the internal business environment includes factors within the organization that impact the approach and success of your operations. The external environment consists of a variety of factors outside your company doors that you typically don't have much control over.

First of all, I would like to get a review of the key factors of the environment of indirect effect. They are:

- Changes in the Development Strategy of the Country and Separate Legislative Acts

It is important to develop tourism in Russia in general and separate regions in particular. The large-scale events (The 2014 Olympic Winter Games, International Summits, Summer Universiade, International biathlon competitions, Future FIFA World Cup 2018) gave a significant impetus to the development of tourism business in Kazan, Sochi, Vladivostok, Khanty–Mansiysk and other cities. Moreover, the special recreational areas and tourist clusters are rapidly growing and developing. However, there is the unevenness in the development of hotel business. The leaders are still Moscow and St. Petersburg (Dzhandzhugazova, Zaitseva, Larionova & Pervunin 2015, 291). Thus, at the beginning of 2016 about 523 hotels with a total capacity of about 31 thousand rooms in Moscow; 44 of them worked under the famous and well-known international hotel brand-names (Russia in Figures. 2016, 168.). At the same time, lots of objects and facilities that were built and still are under the construction. It means the figures are growing.

- Socio–Political Factors

Nowadays the Russian Federation is not perceived positively in the international community but the situation is changing. There were some instabilities between the EU and Russia and between Russia and Turkey. Based on the number of tourist arrivals and statistics on tourist flows, the study reveals that the international tourism market is indirectly affected by this situation. Thus, number of inbound tourism trips in 2014 was 25438, in 2015 — 26852. Number of outbound tourism trips in 2014 was 42921, in 2015 — 34390 (Russia in Figures 2016, 168–170.).

- Macro–Economic Factors

At least the materials of study published on Federal Tourism Agency of the Ministry of Culture of the Russian Federation official website shows that after some economic instabilities in the country almost 80% of Russians decided to cut their cost on holidays. They prefer to stay at home. 17% is choosing the Russian Federation as the place for their holidays and only 3% plan to visit foreign countries.

- The Image of the Russian Hotel Business, its Formation and Promotion in Foreign Countries

Unfortunately, there are many different publications about the expensiveness of hotel services in Russia as well as about the noncompliance of prices and quality of services provided. For example, according to the study of TripIndex Room Service 2013, Moscow was called the most expensive city. But now the situation is changing. Not surprisingly, Scandinavia emerged as the most expensive region on the index, with Nordic cities claiming four of the top 10 most expensive spots. After Helsinki, Oslo, Stockholm and Copenhagen also made the list. Moscow is not so expensive nowadays. At the same time, the situation with quality is changing. Many Russian and foreign people said that it become well (Russian public opinion research center, 2016).

• Demographic Factors and Personnel Training

The demographic situation in Russia is quite complicated today. The population of people under the age of 30 is decreasing, in consequence of which the employers have to pay more attention to the older generation (over 50 years). It is harder to work with such people and they do not simply ready to work in the service sector. There was another education system in Russia when they studied. (Zaitseva 2013, 330.)

Moreover, the share of experts with specialized education from the amount of University graduates are not growing and will even significantly reduce in the future (Russia in Figures 2016, 148.).

Furthermore, nowadays the so-called generation Y (people born in the period from 1981 to 2000 and who are now up to 35 years) is in the great demand; in 3–4 years the new generation Z will also approach the labor market (Russia in Figures 2016, 80.). There will be a problem with mobility. Employees changed their jobs very often (such people prefer working in the same place within few years and then moves to a new working place and doing so few times during his life) (Dzhandzhugazova, Zaitseva, Larionova & Pervunin 2015, 295).

But there are some positive tendencies: decrease of unemployment rate, change in the system of interaction between employers and higher education system. If earlier the employers generally did not express much of desire to co-operate with the higher and secondary professional education institutions now they are actively co-operate with the relevant educational institutions, conduct the integrated lectures, organize various workshops and excursions to hotels. In other words, the main task they have is to attract the prospective university students to join service Universities and colleges and then to invite them to practical training choosing the most capable and customer-focused people. Another question is that the share of appropriate candidates who can be trained to work in the front-office area and who are ready to work for, as usually, low wages is also low. It is a typical situation for small towns. (Zaitseva 2013, 330.)

What is more, the new competition becomes popular in Russia. It is named WorldSkills. As stated by organizers, WorldSkills is the global contest for skills excellence and development. Through international cooperation and development between industry, government, organizations, and institutions, it promotes the benefits of and need for skilled professionals through grass-roots community projects, skill competitions, and knowledge exchange. It shows how important skills education and training is for youth, industries and society by challenging young professionals around the world to become the best in the skill of their choice. Experts said that WorldSkills will be the global hub for skills excellence and development with ongoing activities nationally, regionally and globally. (Wilde & Rely, 2015) So, educational institutions start to understand that it is very important to cooperate with employers if you want to be a professional nowadays.

Conclusion

It is obvious that the hotel business in Russia has a lot of problems but it has great prospects for further development. Moreover, the situation is changing in a right way. However, for effective work, it is necessary to monitor the changes in the above mentioned key factors constantly.

References:

1. Dzhandzhugazova E. A., Zaitseva N. A., Larionova A. A., & Pervunin S. N. 2015. The Russian Hotel Market: Condition and Development Under the Crisis. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 6, 3, pp. 289–296.
2. Federal Tourism Agency of the Ministry of Culture of the Russian Federation. <http://russiaturism.ru/en>. Accessed: 2.10.2016.
3. International Hotel Chains. *Middle East Journal of Scientific Research*, 14,3, pp. 328–334.
4. Ovcharov A. O., Vasiljeva M. V., & Shirin S. S. 2015. The Russian Tourist Industry: Structure, Trends, Competitiveness at the World Market, 7, 9, pp.151–161.

5. Russia in Figures 2016. http://www.gks.ru/free_doc/doc_2016/rusfig/rus16e.pdf. Accessed: 15.10.2016
6. Russian public opinion research center. <http://wciom.com/>. Accessed: 16.10.2016
7. Zaitseva, N.A. 2013. The Forecast of Development of the Hotel Business in Russia as a Promising Direction of Business Expansion of International Hotel Chains. Middle East Journal of Scientific Research, 14,3, pp. 328–334.

Список литературы:

1. Джанджугазова Е. А., Зайцева Н. А., Ларионова А. А., Первунин С. Н. Российский рынок отелей: условие и развитие при кризисе // Среднерусский журнал общественных наук, 2015. № 6, 3, С. 289-296.
2. Федеральная служба туризма министерства культуры Российской Федерации. <http://russiaturism.ru/en>. Полученный доступ: 10.02.2016.
3. Международные Гостиничные сети // Ближний Восток Журнал научных исследований, 14,3, стр 328-334.
4. Овчаров А. О., Васильева М. V, Ширин С. С. 2015. Российский Туристический бизнес: Структура, Тенденции, Конкурентоспособность на Мировом рынке, 7, 9, pp.151–161.
5. Россия 2016 в цифрах. http://www.gks.ru/free_doc/doc_2016/rusfig/rus16e.pdf. Полученный доступ: 15.10.2016
6. Российский научно-исследовательский центр общественного мнения. <http://wciom.com/>. Полученный доступ: 16.10.2016
7. Зайцева Н. А. Прогноз развития Гостиничного бизнеса в России как Многообещающее Направление Делового Расширения Международных Гостиничных сетей. // Среднерусский журнал общественных наук, 2013. 14,3. С. 328-334.

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